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To,

Dr. Ravindra Pratap Singh

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Dated: 3rd March, 2014

Dear Dr. Singh,

This is to acknowledge the receipt of research paper entitled, **Locational Analysis of 'OCP' Settlements in Jhajjar Lowland, Haryana** (by Yashpal, R.P. Singh and V. Pawar)for the publication in our journal *Manaviki*. On behalf of the Editorial Board of the Journal, I am pleased to inform you that the paper submitted by you has been accepted and will be published in Vol. IV (2) of the journal.

Looking forward for your valuable contribution in future also.

Sincerely Yours,

R. N. Singh
(Dr. R. N. Singh)
Chief Editor

Locational Analysis of 'OCP' Settlements in Jhajjar Lowland, Haryana

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Introduction:

Seeing the problem of the 'OCP' in Indian archaeology as it is connected with early Harappan as well as mature Harappan even to late Harappan culture as the cultural remains highlights. The geographical conditions create barriers and opportunities, based on technological expertise, social, political and economic organization of the societies. So it is imperative to have general feel of the geographical setting of a region which play an important role in the origins, development and dissemination of cultures. It helps to understand cultural responses to nature through labour. It is true that Marx speaks of labour as a process between man and nature. But the terms of this interaction are man, through his own actions, mediates, regulates and controls the metabolism between himself and nature by working on objects of labour that are spontaneously provided by nature.ⁱ

Geographical Background:

India divided into four major macro regions depending upon the physiographic characteristics namely the Northern Mountains, the Great Plains, the Deccan Plateau and the Coastal Plains and Islands. These are further divided into meso regions, which in turn further divided into micro-regions, and sub-micro region because of differences in their respective natural resources, climatic and geographical conditions.ⁱⁱ The area of study falls under macro region of 'the Great Plains'. Because of rainfall, soils and drainage the Great Plains have been divided into seven meso-regions and twenty four micro-regions. The Great Plains include the Punjab plains, the Haryana plains, the Arid Rajasthan plains, the Upper Ganga plains, the Middle Ganga plains and the Lower Ganga plains as meso regions. The OCP culture spread over the Rajasthan plains, the Haryana plains, and the Upper Ganga plains.ⁱⁱⁱ The average elevation of Indo-Gangetic plains is ranges from about 150 metre near sea level to about 300 metre in Punjab and upper Ganga plains near the Himalaya foot-hills. These plains have almost uniform topography, though the nature of the material brought down by the rivers varies significantly, resulting in local geo morphological variations.^{iv}

The study area is a part of Jhajjar Low Land covering villages of Jhajjar tehsil, Haryana (Figure 1). The study area is consisting of coarse loam (*Dahar and Chaeknote*) and Aeolian sand (*Thali*). The study area contains 144 villages and 2 towns, i.e. Jhajjar and Beri.

Exploration and Findings:

1. Amadal-Shahpur (28°32'10"N; 76°28'18"E) OCP, LH and EHi:

The site is located 500metre southwest of the village and known as *Bani ka Khera* in local parlance. The site is situated upon 10 feet high aeolian sand dune. The area of the site is about 2800 square metre. On the south of the site there is a big natural depression. The pottery shreds collected from the surface of the site include late Harappan, incised decorated OCP and Early Historical (EHi) times.^v I do not found the cultural representative of Late Harappan (LH) and OCP during my visit to the site.

2. Aurangpur (28°31'50"N; 76°43'08"E) OCP and LH:

The site is located about 2kilometre west of the village. The site is situated on 10 feet high aeolian sand dune. The site covers an area of 6000 square metre. The drain number 8 passes through the west side of the site at a distance of one kilometre. There is a large natural depression on the western side of the side. The cultural remains include Late Harappan and OCP shreds. J.S. Rahar did not mention the occurrence of OCP but during my visit to the site I collected incised ochre colour pottery shreds from the site.^{vi}

3. Babra (28°34'08"N; 76°38'19"E) OCP and LH:

The site is located about one kilometre south of the village and is known as *Guga peer wala* in local parlance. The site is situated on 10 feet high aeolian sand dune. The area of the site is about 5000 square metre. The drain number 8 flows through the southern side of the site at a distance of 500 metre. The cultural material collected from the surface of the site include wheel made, well fired, unslipped and incised decorated OCP and late Harappan pot shreds. The antiquity comprised of *idli* shaped terracotta discs.^{vii}

4. Batehra-I (28°27'50"N; 76°40'30"E) H, OCP and LH:

The site is situated about 300 metre southwest of the village on a 15 feet high aeolian sand dune. The area of the site is about 20000 square metre. There are natural depressions on the west, east and north side of the site. The cultural material gathered from the surface of the site includes Harappan (H), Late Harappan and incised decorated OCP shreds.

5. Batehra-II (28°27'50"N; 76°42'00"E) OCP, LH, EHi and M:

The another ancient settlement in the village Batehra is located at a distance of 1.5 kilometre on the southeastern side on 15 feet high mound of aeolian sand. The area of the site is about 20000 square metre. There is natural depression all around the site. The cultural material recovered from the surface of the site includes Late Harappan and OCP shreds along with Early Historical and Medieval (M) times.

6. Chandpur (28°29'15"N; 76°38'45"E) OCP and LH:

The site is located about one kilometre west of the village on a 10 feet high aeolian sand dune. and is known as *dahri* in local parlance. The area of the site is about 12000 square metre. There is natural depression all around the site. The cultural material recovered from the surface of the site comprised of less fired, red slipped shreds of OCP and late Harappan times.

7. Dawla (28°03'10"N; 76°35'51"E) OCP and LH:

The site is located about two kilometre west of the village on a 8 feet high Aeolian sand dune and is known as *Sahiwala khera* in local parlance. The area of the site is about 20000 square metre. There is a pond on the northern side of the site. The cultural material recovered from the surface of the site includes incised decorated and red slipped shreds of OCP with some shreds resembling early Harappan, late Harappan pottery. The incised decorations consist of chevron pattern and rows of oblique dashes. This site comprised of OCP and late Harappan pottery. J.S.Rahar also reported mature Harappan pottery from this site, which I was unable to notice^{viii}.

8. Ghudda (28°38'30"N; 76°48'30"E) OCP and LH:

The site is located at a distance of two kilometre from the village in northwest direction on a 5 feet high clayey mound and known as *Ujjar Khera* in local parlance. The area of the site is about 10000 square metre. A rain channel passes through the northeastern side of the site. The cultural

material recovered from the surface of the site comprised of OCP and late Harappan pot shreds. The OCP shreds are less fired having red slip and ochreous colour. Pieces of copper ring also recovered from the site.^{ix}

9. Jhajjar (28°37'10"N; 76°39'00"E) OCP, LH, EH and M:

The site is located behind the Lawrence school near the medieval monuments on Jhajjar-Rohtak highway. The area of the site is about 20000 square metre and situated on 5 feet high clayey mound. There is a natural depression on the northern side of the site. The Jhajjar drain passes from the south side of the site at a distance of 300 metre. The cultural material collected from the surface of the site includes shreds of late Harappan, OCP, early historical and medieval wares.^x

10. Kamelgarh (28°37'45"N; 76°41'25"E) OCP and LH:

The site is located 1.5 kilometre northeast of the village in *Baniawala khet*. The area of the site is about 8000 square metre and located on 5 feet high red clayey soil. There is natural depression on the eastern side of the site. The pottery is very much corroded due to salt efflorescence but in appearance it looks like OCP and late Harappan.^{xi}

11. Kasni (28°30'18"N; 76°35'22"E) OCP and LH:

The site is located toward the western side of the village at a distance of 200 metre. The site is located on a 5 feet high mound of clayey soil. The site covers an area of about 10000 square metre. The cultural deposit is about .80 metre as observed in the trench on the side cutting of the road. Drain number 8 is about 400 metre east from the site. The cultural material collected from the surface of the site comprised of early Harappan, OCP and few shreds of late Harappan pottery.

12. Khatiwas (28°37'30"N; 76°35'15"E) OCP and LH:

The site is located 1.5 kilometre southwest of the village and is known as *Kalal wali thali* in local parlance. The site is situated on a 5 feet high aeolian sand dune. The area of the site is about 20000 square metre. There is a natural depression all around the site. The drain number 8 is about four kilometre from the site in western direction. The cultural material included typical OCP shreds which leaves ochre colour on the fingers when rubbed and few late Harappan shreds.

13. Kheri Khummar (28°37'47"N; 76°37'10"E) OCP and LH:

The site is located 1.5 kilometre north of the village on a 5 feet high aeolian sand mound and is known as *ghurawali* in local parlance. The area of the site is about 20000 square metre. There is natural depression on the west and north side of the site. The cultural material recovered from the surface of the site includes early and late Harappan shreds along with circular terracotta discs. Few shreds having incised decoration and akin to OCP also collected from the site. The incised decoration consist of chevron pattern.

14. Kutani (28°28'45"N; 76°45'00"E) OCP, LH and M:

The site is located about 400 metre east of the village on a 30 feet high aeolian sand dune. The area of the site is about 32000 square metre. The site is surrounded by the *dahar* of Sahibi river on all sides. The cultural material gathered from the surface of the site includes OCP, late Harappan and medieval pot shreds. The antiquity includes *idli* shaped terracotta cake.

15. Machhroli (28°28'10"N; 76°40'15"E) OCP and LH:

The site is located about 1.5 kilometre northeast of the village on aeolian sand *thali* at a height of 15 feet. The area of the site is about 12000 square metre. There is a big natural depression measuring about 300 *bigha* on the northeast side of the site. The cultural material recovered from the surface of the site includes Late Harappan and OCP shreds. The OCP shreds are wheel made, red slipped as well as unslipped, less fired and have ochre colour.

16. Mahrana (28°41'04"N; 76°40'09"E) EH, H, OCP and LH:

The site is located one kilometre east of the village on a 6 feet high grey clayey soil. The area of the site is about 10000 square metre. A rain channel passes from the eastern side of the site. The cultural remains collected from the surface of the site include Early Harappan (EH), Harappan and late Harappan pot shreds. During my visit I also collected incised decorated shreds of OCP.^{xii} The antiquity comprised circular terracotta cakes.

17. Nangala (28°29'45"N; 76°44'15"E) OCP, LH and M:

The site is situated on a 5 feet high aeolian sand dune, 600 metre on the western side of the village and called *Khera* in local parlance. The area of the site is about 8000 square metre. There is natural depression on the east side of the site. The cultural material recovered from the surface of the site includes few OCP and late Harappan shreds along with medieval ware. The OCP shreds include carinated bowls having notched incised decoration on the rib. Moreover, there is an old well on the western side of the site made up of lakhauri bricks and white lime. The depth of the well is about 30 feet and its circumference is about 10 feet.

18. Sikanderpur (28°33'50"N; 76°40'51"E) OCP and LH:

The site is located about 1.5 kilometre northeast of the village in the field of Mr. Leela Ram. The site is situated on 20 feet high aeolian sand dune. The area of the site can't be determined as the site is totally levelled by earth digging but the shreds of late Harappan and OCP affiliation were collected from the remaining section of the dune. A natural depression occurs in the east of the site at a distance of two kilometre.

19. Silani Kesho (28°33'50"N; 76°40'31"E) OCP and LH:

The site is located on the north of the village on the 5 feet high clayey soil mound. There is natural depression on the west of the site. The ceramic industry comprised early and late Harappan pot shreds along with OCP. The area covered by the site is about 7000 square metre.^{xiii}

20. Surha (28°33'10"N; 76°44'05"E) EH, H, LH, OCP, PGW, EH_i and M:

The site is located on the northern side of the village on aeolian sand dune of 10 feet height. The area of the site is about 10000 square metre. The cultural material recovered from the surface of the site include pottery of all the three phases of Harappan culture, OCP, PGW (Painted Grey Ware), EH and medieval times.^{xiv} Drain no. 8 passes from the eastern side of the site. The other findings include terracotta figurines and broken glass bangles of early historical and medieval period.

21. Surhaiti (28°30'18"N; 76°36'60"E) OCP and LH:

The site is located about one kilometre south of the village and known as *Neem Nath* in local parlance. The height of the aeolian sand mound is about 5 feet from the surrounding plain area. The site covers an area of 12000 square metre. Drain number 8 passes from the western side of the site at a distance of one kilometre. Natural depression occurs on all sides of the site except

south where chain of aeolian sand dunes is present. The cultural material recovered from the surface of the site includes OCP and late Harappan shreds along with *idli* shaped terracotta cakes.

22. Talao (28°36'00"N; 76°36'30"E) OCP and EMGW:

The site is located about 2.5 kilometre southwest of the village. The site is situated on a 15 feet high aeolian sand dune and is called as *khera* in local parlance. The area of the site is about 10000 square metre. There is a big natural depression measuring about 100 *bigha* on the southern side of the site. The cultural material recovered from the surface of the site includes incised decorated OCP and Early Medieval Glazed Ware (EMGW) pot shreds. The incised decoration consists of chevron patterns.

Analytical Discussion:

The total number of 54 sites are explored in Jhajjar lowland belonging to various cultural phases ranging from EH, H, OCP/LH to Medieval passing through PGW, GW, RW and Early Medieval. However, most of them are belonging to the OCP settlements in the region. These OCP settlements are further classified in two major groups; i.e. bi-cultural and multi-cultural, according to their cultural affiliation (Figure 2). Further these sites are classified into five size categories namely camp sites having area below 3000m², very small villages (3001-6000m²), small villages (6001-9000m²), big villages (9001-12000m²) and very big villages (more than 12001m²) arbitrarily for the sake of analysis as the cultural material observed do not show the characteristics of township and cities. There is absence of mono-cultural OCP sites in the area shows that the habitation of these sites are also favored by other contemporary and later cultures. Whereas contemporary LH culture observed along with OCP at two third of the total sites (i.e. 22 sites) while only one third is being chosen by the later cultures (Table 1). It shows that the locations occupied by the OCP culture is less preferred in later times and with passage of time people brock the new ground for their habitation.

Table 1: Frequency of OCP Settlements according to Area of the Site in Jhajjar Lowland, Haryana

OCP Settlement Area	<3000m ² [1]	3001-6000m ² [2]	6001-9000m ² [3]	9001-12000m ² [4]	>12000m ² [5]	N. A. [6]	Total
Cultural Category							
Bi-Cultural	-	2	2	6	3	1	14
Multi-Cultural	1	-	1	2	4	-	8
Water Sources							
Rain Channel	-	1	-	4	1	-	6
Natural Depression	1	-	3	3	3	1	11
Stream and Natural Depression	-	-	-	1	1	-	2
Rain Channel and Natural Depression	-	1	-	-	2	-	3
Soil Type							
Aeolian Sand	1	2	-	3	6	1	13
Clayey	-	-	3	5	1	-	9
Total	1	2	3	8	7	1	22

More than two third of total OCP settlements covers an area of more than 9000m². It shows that the people converges at the comparatively secure places where natural resources are concentrated. The most promising locations chosen for habitation at the time were in the vicinity of natural depressions but not the stream and rain channels, probably due to insecurity of flooding as well as water scarcity. It is also observed that settlements of all size categories are located along the natural depressions while along stream and rain channels mainly large settlements were observed. Most likely the demands met with large settlement cannot be fulfilled a limited water resources, like natural depression.

As already cited the soil types available in this area is mainly aeolian sand and clay, where the first is mostly preferred. It is also observed in the region that the clayey soil is not a congenial choice for the small settlements probably due to lack of suitable technology to work it out. Moreover the impervious nature of clayey soil is a deterrent, so the settlement with large population opted the aeolian sand grounds for their habitation.

Conclusion:

The OCP culture spreads over the Great Plains of North-western India having almost uniform topography. The study area is a part of Haryana Plains consisting Jhajjar Low Land covering 144 villages and 2 towns of Jhajjar tehsil. A total of 54 sites were observed during the village to village archaeological field work in the region; out of which 22 settlements belonging to OCP culture are studied in detail. The analysis pointed out that the OCP habitations were not occupied by subsequent cultural settlements rather they were abandoned to a large extent for a lag of time. Although these settlements site were reoccupied in future, but their number was far less as compared to the deserted sites.

The subsequent cultural settlements to OCP are technologically more efficient as iron tools are reported from their cultural repertoire. These technologically competent cultures explored and utilized diverse resources even far from OCP habitations and shifted to new grounds. The OCP settlements congregates in large population at the places of easily available resources to compensate their technological skills. The general trend of location of OCP settlements is mainly on and along the natural depressions as a water source and aeolian sand as a choice for habitation for their subsistence.

Figure 1: Distribution map of OCP settlements in Jhajjar low land, Haryana

Figure 2: Cultural category frequency graph of OCP settlements in Jhajjar Lowland.

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